

integrated with other rights programs such as those for poverty alleviation, women's empowerment, people with disabilities, and empowerment programs for marginalized groups.

- Family members are the leading providers of care for the elderly. Giving proper care to an elderly person at home requires special knowledge and skills. Therefore, short training for family members on "Caring for the Elderly at Home" can be planned. Health centers and health care providers can be trained to train coaches' (ToT) who can further train elderly family members in the community.
- National policies on aging, supported by home-based care, would highlight the importance of enabling the elderly to live close to the community, thus taking an important qualitative step in improving the elderly. What is required in this situation is a model that would enable aging through economic efficiency and sustainability.

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Leadership and its impact on the challenges of higher education

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Abstract

Leadership can be defined as the ability of a leader to influence his employees, in such a way that they cooperate and contribute to the efforts oriented towards the realization of the goals of the educational institution. One of the challenges of the institutions, implemented in the market, is the selection of leaders who will represent the mission and vision of the educational institution.

The vision and mission of an institution should be represented by a leader with a contemporary outlook, who conveys to employees an inspiring and collaborative organizational behavior.

One of the concerns of institutions in recent years is the inefficient and inefficient organization of work. Therefore, the current leaders, who enjoy this status, must leave these wrong structures, in order to create harmony and organization among their subordinates. Organizing work with deadlines and division of tasks according to the specializations of the employee, will bring productivity and achieve objectives in a timely manner.

In the conditions of comprehensive changes of society, economy and politics, throughout the process of democratization and the prospects of EU membership, higher education in Albania is in constant transformation and reform from a state-controlled system to a liberalized higher education.

Key words: work, leadership, team, Europe 2020 Strategy

Introduction

Leadership and its characteristics

Leadership or leadership is the process of influencing an individual over a certain group of people, in achieving common goals.

By this is meant, the creation of mutual relations between the leader and the group, influencing the realization of the goals of an institution through joint actions.

For an organization, leadership is very important when it comes to the process of organizing and managing situations, development or well-being of work in that institution.

A leader must be visionary, have a vision of achieving common goals but also be open to the group (his followers) and accept the views of group members. The leadership process should not exclude even one member of the group to display his / her visions and way of achieving goals.

Early understanding of leadership relies primarily on identifying persons who possess special personal qualities and abilities.

Leadership and management

In recent decades there has been an intense debate over the relationship between leadership and management. Leadership, in many ways is similar to management. The leader, like the manager, is faced with achieving the goal, working with different individuals, and many managerial functions are the same as defining leadership. But these two concepts are not identical.

Other scholars also point out in their research that there are fundamental differences between management and leadership. The role of the Manager is to plan, organize and coordinate. The role of the Leader is to inspire and motivate.

Differences between leader and manager

- The manager focuses on control
- The leader inspires to increase trust in him
- The manager prioritizes the short-term perspective- The leader takes care of the long-term perspective
- The manager deals with the How and When questions while the leader deals with the What and Why questions
- The manager accepts the status quo- The leader challenges him
- The manager represents the good soldier- The leader has his UNI

Effective Leadership

Essentially, prominent leaders become a fine balance between traits, abilities, behaviors, sources of power, and aspects of the situation.

These become determinants of the ability to influence followers and achieve group goals.

The most effective measure of a leader and his / her competence is the degree to which the group achieves its goals. Effective leadership begins with developing a vision, a desire or a picture of what an institution / school will look like in the future. Effective leadership begins with the basic skill that is self-confidence, including a maturity, conviction, and expertise, which translates into a goal and direction. It is this clarity of vision that gives leaders great confidence to embrace the role of instilling motivation, self-esteem, and teamwork.

Effective leaders fully understand their environment and can transform situations, to achieve a reinforced vision.

To understand the behavior and traits of an effective leader you need to look at their innate characteristics. The most important are energy level, physical endurance and stress tolerance.

Positive energy and stress tolerance help to deal with the fast pace and frequent chaotic events of the institution.

Effective leadership brings unwavering demands, which require physical vitality and a high degree of emotional resilience. Requires the ability, to solve the problem and to solve short-term or long-term problems. An effective leader must be flexible with ideas and open to a variety of solutions and views.

Practical cases of effective leadership

We have mentioned above that leadership learns, forms, and develops from long life experience, and the impact of practices on well-structured leadership is numerous.

Leadership Modeling- Leaders set the principles, regarding how people should be treated and how goals should be pursued. They set standards of excellence and then set an example for others to follow. The prospect of complex change can confuse employees and stifle action, so they set temporary goals so that people can achieve small victories, which lead them to big goals.

Inspiration in vision communication- Leaders strongly believe they can make a difference. They envision the future, creating an ideal and unique image of what the institution or school can be a model of success. Through their implementation and persuasion, leaders invite others into their dreams. They breathe life into the life of the institution, into their visions and create spaces to conceive of the future.

Process Challenge - Leaders seek opportunities to change the status quo. In doing so they experiment and take risks, even though they know that taking risks involves mistakes and failures, they accept inevitable disappointments as opportunities to learn.

Enabling others to take action- Leaders foster collaboration and build vibrant teams. They actively involve others. Leaders understand that mutual respect is what keeps extraordinary efforts, creating a warm and motivating environment. They empower others, making each person feel capable and powerful.

Encourage employees- Fulfilling extraordinary things in the institution is hard work. To keep hope and determination alive, leaders recognize the contributions individuals make. In each winning team, members must participate in the respective awards, to be as motivated and effective as possible.

Challenges of higher education in Albania within the priorities of the ‘Europe 2020’ Strategy

The draft of the new National Strategy for Development and Integration (2014-2020) reconfirms this role of higher education and defines as priorities the quality of higher education;

- Profiling of universities according to the development needs of the country and the labor market;
- Re-evaluating the sharing of the cost of higher education with students as well as improving the internal governance of universities by combining autonomy, accountability with good governance.

In the conditions of comprehensive changes of society, economy and politics, throughout the process of democratization and the prospects of EU membership, higher education in Albania is in constant transformation and reform from a state-controlled system to a liberalized higher education.

Two of the most important developments in this transformation process have been:

- Implementation of the Bologna Process and efforts to become part of the European Higher Education Area and the European Research Area;
- Liberalization of higher education and licensing of private universities as an alternative to state ones

Europa 2020 Strategy

The EUROPA 2020 strategy specifically addresses five key areas: employment, innovation, education, poverty alleviation and climate / energy. Achieving the objectives is closely linked not only to efforts at EU level, but also to their translation into concrete policies in the member states as well as aspirations to become part of the EU.

An important dimension of the EUROPA 2020 growth strategy is also higher education, research and innovation.

In order to achieve a more qualitative, sustainable and inclusive growth, EUROPA needs more graduates equipped with the right knowledge and skills to meet the challenges of the labor market and contemporary society.

The modernization of higher education, the further development of research and innovation are seen as dimensions that will contribute to university education,

making it possible to adapt to the pandemic situation, given that teaching did not take place in classrooms, but through online platforms.

Improving the quality of higher education

- Adaptation of teaching and learning methodology according to student diversity;
- Utilizing the potential of information and communication technologies;
- Study programs that are based on and adapt to the demands of the labor market;
- Quality assurance;
- Business connections;
- Employment of graduates

Conclusions

- An effective leader needs to be flexible with ideas and open to a variety of solutions and views.
- Effective communication within the institution is very important both for the realization of change, as well as for the support and protection of a policy, or a certain way of management.
- Senior executives should build “communication bridges” with the external environment to facilitate contacts and resolve potential problems.
- In the conditions of comprehensive changes of society, economy and politics, throughout the process of democratization and prospects of EU membership, higher education in Albania is in constant transformation and reform from a state-controlled system to a liberalized system of higher education.

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